

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKINTUNDE****FIRST NAME: TEMITOPE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the basic information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unnecessary text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is less than 5%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your seven key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Introduction to academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-8)
2. The process of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 8-10)
3. The fundamentals of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10-12)
4. Punctuation and language variants (EUCLID 2021, 15-22; 24-32)
5. The importance of style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. Plagiarism and the possible impact on academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
7. Conclusion

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

After reading through the ACA-401D course pack for period one, I understood better the need for academic essay writing. While there are different types of essay writing, the academic ones reflect a more formal structure and use of language. While it may seem like a refresher course in the English language, I also found out that there were lots of things that I either overlooked or did not even know at all about the English language. I also realized the importance of response papers shaping my thoughts and opinions from my course materials.

For the period one response paper, I intend to discuss the fundamentals of academic writing and the impact of writing patterns and appropriate punctuation on academic essay writing. I will also examine the importance of style guides and the dangers of plagiarism in academic essay writing.

2) THE FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

Structures are essential fundamentals to provide writers with guidance in academic essay writing. EUCLID (2021, 10-11) implies a structure with an introduction, body, and conclusion. While x-raying the framework of academic essays, the writer is expected to include the essay topic. The introduction section should also contain how the issue is relevant to the process, course materials, and framework for the writing.

The body is next, which contains the main content, including the proof and its analysis, and leading statements to the next section of the body (EUCLID 2021, 10). The proper alignment of this information and materials into sub-sections. As a writer, it is essential that my writing is evidence-based and, in some cases, empirical evidence-based facts should be presented in Academic Essay Writing to argue one's position effectively.

The author highlights their position on the research question for the conclusion section while providing a recap of the main ideas from the body section (EUCLID 2021, 10).

a) The Process of Academic Essay Writing

To examine the fundamentals of academic essay writing, A key starting point is to learn the process of it. While all forms of essay writing may have some similar features, academic essays have a process that must be duly followed: identification of the problem, research, critical thinking, planning, and writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-15). I understand from the course text how important it is to mentally envisage your writing as this will help develop your context and content for writing. (EUCLID 2021, 9).

After defining the writing scope, the next activity is gathering resources that explain the writing task. The scholarly perspective of Academic essays differentiates them from other forms of essays. As a result, materials for academic essays must be from viable educational resources only (EUCLID 2021, 8). To get critical information from academic essay materials, I had to do essential reading and appraisal of the materials. I sometimes try putting myself in the authors' thoughts and minds to analyze the materials properly.

After the information has been gathered and organized into a writing plan or form, academic writers need to examine the question at hand while aligning with the data collected to get opinions and proof that agrees or disagrees with the answer (EUCLID 2021, 9-10).

b) Punctuation and Language Variants

A distinctive feature of academic essay writing is the proper use of punctuation and the adequate identification of language variants.

Punctuations give life to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 15-17). For instance, the comma will help a reader understand which words go together and which parts of your sentences are most important. Misusing commas may confuse the reader, signal ignorance of writing rules, or indicate carelessness. (EUCLID 2021, 19-20). They are used to identify non-defining clauses, words, or phrases according to placement in sentences. Full stops are used to end a sentence. They indicate that a point has been made and that we're ready to move on to the following sentence. Like other punctuation marks, they show us how to read sentences and when they end.

EUCLID (2021, 25) and the tutorial guide identifies the importance of using a chosen language variant of the English language as it helps provide consistency and meaning in academic essays. The key variants are the British and American (EUCLID 2021, 25). These two language variants sometimes have different spellings of some words but the same pronunciation and, at times, the exact spelling but different pronunciations. Also, some words may be the exact spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. The use of punctuation, especially the comma, also differs.

i) *The importance of style guides*

As I read through the definition of a style guide in EUCLID (2021, 41), it implies that “A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing styles that need to be consistent.” I pondered this definition and noted that it is something that creative writers have always used to make their writing attractive to the reader. When style guides are in use, it helps you understand the author’s perspective while still being able to make your own opinion about the content and context of the writing.

ii) *Plagiarism and the possible impact on academic essays*

A distinctive feature in academic essay writing is the ability to think independently and creatively; that is the Originality of the Author. Originality, according to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, is: (1) the quality or state of being original, (2) freshness of aspect, design, or style (3) the power of independent thought or constructive imagination. From these definitions, originality identifies and separates one writing from another.

Plagiarism is when a writer fails to acknowledge the source of information in an academic paper (EUCLID 2021, 34). This implies that a lack of originality can be regarded as plagiarism.

In academic essay writing, plagiarism can be explained as direct quotes from a source, improper paraphrasing, or a direct duplication of ideas without giving credit to or referencing the start of the information (EUCLID 2021, 33-35). Citations are allowed as theoretical methods to avoid plagiarism. Quotations are used through in-text and a list of cited references.

3) CONCLUSION

In writing this response paper, I can have a more robust understanding of the course ACA-401D. I asked myself some questions, which I also answered myself; this gave me a deeper understanding of the processes, rules, and preferences that define academic writing. A student needs to understand the process and fundamentals of developing an academic essay. Furthermore, the student should also be familiar with the rules of plagiarism, the importance of adopting a style guide that can be combined with language variants, and the proper use of punctuation.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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